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Fundamentals in a Complex Simulator for a Resultant Combination in Logic Design

History
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Introduction

The basic concept of the logic gate is that it is the basic block of a digital circuit that possesses two inputs and one output, the relationship in the input-output is based on certain logic (Isiaka and Sharji (2024); White-side et al. (2022); Bonnerjee et al. (2019); Li et al. (2013); Lee (2014); Pourshaghghi (2009); Deng et al. (2022); POURSHAGHAGHI et al. (2010,?); Mahmoud et al. (2020); Wen et al. (2005)). The logical gates are both implemented using electronic switch control blocks similar to transistors and diodes. In practice, the logic gates are built using CMOS technology and metal oxide semiconductor FETs, the logic gates are used in microprocessors and microcontrollers for embedded system applications and also in an electronic circuit, they are usually categorised into seven *AND*, *OR*, *XOR*, *NAND*, *NOR*, *XNOR* and *NOT*. In the computational modelling of digital systems, the logic design is the basic organisation of the circuitry of a

digital computer (Volpentesta et al. (2023); Schnabel (2015); Zhelnin (2024); Jun et al. (2024); Bhargava (2019); Alcocer (2023); Ciula et al. (2023); Tanida et al. (2021); Grantcharov et al. (2022)) , which is based on a two-valued logic system, i.e. the input-output,

on-off, yes-no. The computers perform

calculations using components which are logic gates and made up of integrated circuits that receive an input signal by processing it and changing it into an output signal. The basic components of the gates are passed as blocks on a clock pulse as it travels through them (Sharma et al. (2024); Skorupski and Romaniuk (2024)), and the output bits of the control gates are made to control other gates or the output of the results. In the Boolean algebra, there are three likely basic kinds of logic gates which are *AND*, and outputs the value 1 if both inputs are 1; *OR*, which outputs the value 1 if either input is 1; and the *NOT*, which

outputs 1 if the input is 0 and outputs 0;

NOT(NOT – OR), which outputs 1 if both inputs are 0; *XOR(orOR)*, which outputs 1 if only one input is 1; and *XNOR (or EXNOR)*; which outputs 0 if only one input is 1 (Figure 1). Connecting the logic gates makes a device constructive and performs basic arithmetic functions.

Abstract: This paper holds a brief methodology in the fundamentals of logic design simulation-based modelling with analytics that integrate block components. The simulation analysis and modelling techniques are considered together with the resulting output and advancement in modern logic design analytics. Two brief examples were illustrated as a base for the future design of 3D representation of logical design and demonstrate how we can dramatically develop efficient logical events simulation of the models. The problems highlighted started with an introduction to logic gates and a simple performance estimation that progressed to dynamic multiple logical stepwise processes for 2-4 bit logic design.

Keywords: Logic gates, Modelling, Simulation, Design analytics, Logical events, Logic control blocks

In the schematic logic design of a 2-bit multiplexer (Figure 2) the artificial evolution is obtained as well as been based on a Boolean expression, the input and output ($q1$ and $q2$) of the logic gate and its circuit is plotted based on a standard table to give a visual representation of the switching function of the system. The table is reproduced to represent the Boolean expression of the logic gate function which is commonly called the truth table (Figure 3) that shows the possible output of combination to the gate with the resultant depending upon the combination of the inputs. Figure 1 is an example of a single 2-input logic circuit with the input variable labeled as x , x^1 , and x^2 , therefore, there are four possible input combinations i.e. 2^2 of both "OFF" and "ON" for the two inputs. In other words, when dealing with Boolean expressions and especially on the logic gate truth table (Figure 3), one can get a general use of the "on" and "offset" of the controls and give them bit values that can represent the logic level "1" and "0" respectively.

Method and Results

The method adopted for the digital circuits design is used as a tool for the modeling and simulation of its resultant output and truth table, in the digital electronic, the arithmetic and logic unit (ALU) is both a *logicCircuits* digital circuit that performs integer arithmetic and logical operations. The simple ALU is a fundamental building block for the central processing unit of the computer system, even the simplest microprocessors contain a one-purpose arrangement such that maintaining timers has to be combinational. The processors are found inside the modern CPUs and the graphics processing units (GPU) can accommodate very powerful and complex ALUs, one of the most visual cases is that a single component may contain several ALUs that are conceptualised. The majority of the processor's operations are performed by one or more ALUs. This can load data from input registers. The external control unit instructs an ALU to operate and perform data sequencing which is stored as results in the output registers. The control units are responsible for the moving of the process data to and from the registers in the memory. A typical example of a two-bit ALU (Figure 4) was designed using the *logicCircuits* tool which is capable of simulating and producing the truth table within a minimal simulation speed with time. The diagram and vector drawing allow for add and drop procedures which are user-friendly and are extended with electrical engineering solutions from the logic design in the engineering solution park.

The truth table (Figure 5) is used to help show the function of the 2-bit ALU, if the configuration is based on doubt i.e. if the combination is not accurate the report is usually set to error and an unresponsive assembly. The logic circuit combination uses the truth table as a form of expression of the gate circuit. The gate circuit

can be expressed using a common method known as the truth table construct, the table includes all the input rational state combinations that are as high as 1 and as low as 0 for every terminal of the logic gate through the equivalent output level that is similar to on and off. The *NOT* gate is extremely easy to operate. The similarity of the truth table to its logic design is very complex, the concept is based on the fact each result output of the truth table must contain many rows for the possibility of an exclusive combination of inputs. If the *NOT* gate is present, there are likely two possible inputs (0 or 1), and two outputs of four possibilities like 00, 01, 10, and 11, hence it includes four rows for the equivalent truth table. For a 3-input combination, there are 8 possible inputs with 000, 001, 011, 100, 101, 110, and 111. Therefore, the truth table includes 8 rows in its requirements. The computational process requires two to increase the power for the input terminals.

Conclusion

This paper demonstrates a simple introduction to deriving the fundamentals in an analytic complex simulator for a resultant combination in logic design, the simulation analysis and modelling techniques are considered together with result output and coercive with advancement in modern logic design analytics. Two brief examples were demonstrated as a base for the future design of 3D representation of logical design and demonstrate how we can dramatically develop efficient logical events simulation of the models. The problems highlighted started with an introduction to logic gates and a simple performance estimation and progressed to dynamic multiple logical stepwise processes for 2-4 bit logic design and modelling. The future perspective would be to use this as a preliminary introduction to logic design and simulation and develop a custom 3D analytical logic design tool with maximum speed and simulation procedures. The output would produce results that are both graphically presentable and user-friendly for classroom analysis.

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Figure 1: The basic logic gates in digital circuitry.

Figure 2: A simple 2-bit Logic gate design of microprocessor.

Truth Table		
x2	q1	q
0	-	1
1	-	0

Figure 3: Truth table for a 2-bit ALU design.

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Figure 4: A complex two-bit microprocessor with 8 inputs and output channels comprises of a light bulb and switch.

Truth Table						
Filter:						
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Invert <input type="button" value="Apply"/>					
x2122	x2121	x212	x211	x21	x2	q
0	0	0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	0	0	1	1
0	0	0	0	1	0	1
0	0	0	0	1	1	1
0	0	0	1	0	0	1
0	0	0	1	0	1	1
0	0	0	1	1	0	1
0	0	0	1	1	1	1
0	0	1	0	0	0	1

Total rows: 64 Displayed rows: 64

Figure 5: Truth table for the complex 2-bit ALU of a microprocessor.

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